

Smarandachely antipodal signed digraphs

P. Siva Kota Reddy[†], B. Prashanth[†] and M. Ruby Salestina[‡]

[†] Department of Mathematics Acharya Institute of Technology,
Bangalore 560090, India

[‡] Department of Mathematics Yuvaraja's College, University of Mysore,
Mysore 570005, India

E-mail: pskreddy@acharya.ac.in bbprashanth@yahoo.com
salestina@rediffmail.com

Abstract A *Smarandachely k -signed digraph* (*Smarandachely k -marked digraph*) is an ordered pair $S = (D, \sigma)$ ($S = (D, \mu)$) where $D = (V, \mathcal{A})$ is a digraph called *underlying digraph* of S and $\sigma : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k)$ ($\mu : V \rightarrow (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k)$) is a function, where each $\bar{e}_i \in \{+, -\}$. Particularly, a Smarandachely 2-signed digraph or Smarandachely 2-marked digraph is called abbreviated a *signed digraph* or a *marked digraph*. In this paper, we define the Smarandachely antipodal signed digraph $\vec{A}(D)$ of a given signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ and offer a structural characterization of antipodal signed digraphs. Further, we characterize signed digraphs S for which $S \sim \vec{A}(S)$ and $\bar{S} \sim \vec{A}(S)$ where \sim denotes switching equivalence and $\vec{A}(S)$ and \bar{S} denotes the Smarandachely antipodal signed digraph and complementary signed digraph of S respectively.

Keywords Smarandachely k -signed digraphs, Smarandachely k -marked digraphs, balance, switching, Smarandachely antipodal signed digraphs, negation.

§1. Introduction

For standard terminology and notion in digraph theory, we refer the reader to the classic text-books of Bondy and Murty ^[1] and Harary et al. ^[3]; the non-standard will be given in this paper as and when required.

A *Smarandachely k -signed digraph* (*Smarandachely k -marked digraph*) is an ordered pair $S = (D, \sigma)$ ($S = (D, \mu)$) where $D = (V, \mathcal{A})$ is a digraph called *underlying digraph* of S and $\sigma : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k)$ ($\mu : V \rightarrow (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k)$) is a function, where each $\bar{e}_i \in \{+, -\}$. Particularly, a Smarandachely 2-signed digraph or Smarandachely 2-marked digraph is called abbreviated a *signed digraph* or a *marked digraph*. A *signed digraph* is an ordered pair $S = (D, \sigma)$, where $D = (V, \mathcal{A})$ is a digraph called *underlying digraph* of S and $\sigma : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{+, -\}$ is a function. A *marking* of S is a function $\mu : V(D) \rightarrow \{+, -\}$. A signed digraph S together with a marking μ is denoted by S_μ . A signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ is *balanced* if every semicycle of S is positive (Harary et al. ^[3]). Equivalently, a signed digraph is balanced if every semicycle has an even number of negative arcs. The following characterization of balanced signed digraphs is obtained by E. Sampathkumar et al. ^[5].

Proposition 1.1.^[5] A signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ is balanced if, and only if, there exist a marking μ of its vertices such that each arc \vec{uv} in S satisfies $\sigma(\vec{uv}) = \mu(u)\mu(v)$.

Let $S = (D, \sigma)$ be a signed digraph. Consider the marking μ on vertices of S defined as follows: each vertex $v \in V$, $\mu(v)$ is the product of the signs on the arcs incident at v . *Complement* of S is a signed digraph $\bar{S} = (\bar{D}, \sigma')$, where for any arc $e = \vec{uv} \in \bar{D}$, $\sigma'(\vec{uv}) = \mu(u)\mu(v)$. Clearly, \bar{S} as defined here is a balanced signed digraph due to Proposition 1.1.

In ^[5], the authors define switching and cycle isomorphism of a signed digraph as follows:

Let $S = (D, \sigma)$ and $S' = (D', \sigma')$, be two signed digraphs. Then S and S' are said to be *isomorphic*, if there exists an isomorphism $\phi : D \rightarrow D'$ (that is a bijection $\phi : V(D) \rightarrow V(D')$ such that if \vec{uv} is an arc in D then $\vec{\phi(u)\phi(v)}$ is an arc in D') such that for any arc $\vec{e} \in D$, $\sigma(\vec{e}) = \sigma'(\phi(\vec{e}))$. For switching in signed graphs and some results involving switching refer the paper ^[4].

Given a marking μ of a signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, *switching* S with respect to μ is the operation changing the sign of every arc \vec{uv} of S by $\mu(u)\sigma(\vec{uv})\mu(v)$. The signed digraph obtained in this way is denoted by $S_\mu(S)$ and is called μ *switched signed digraph* or just *switched signed digraph*.

Further, a signed digraph S switches to signed digraph S' (or that they are switching equivalent to each other), written as $S \sim S'$, whenever there exists a marking of S such that $S_\mu(S) \cong S'$.

Two signed digraphs $S = (D, \sigma)$ and $S' = (D', \sigma')$ are said to be *cycle isomorphic*, if there exists an isomorphism $\phi : D \rightarrow D'$ such that the sign $\sigma(Z)$ of every semicycle Z in S equals to the sign $\sigma(\phi(Z))$ in S' .

Proposition 1.2.^[4] Two signed digraphs S_1 and S_2 with the same underlying graph are switching equivalent if, and only if, they are cycle isomorphic.

§2. Smarandachely antipodal signed digraphs

In ^[2], the authors introduced the notion antipodal digraph of a digraph as follows: For a digraph $D = (V, \mathcal{A})$, the *antipodal digraph* $\vec{A}(D)$ of $D = (V, \mathcal{A})$ is the digraph with $V(\vec{A}(D)) = V(D)$ and $\mathcal{A}(\vec{A}(D)) = \{(u, v) : u, v \in V(D) \text{ and } d_D(u, v) = \text{diam}(D)\}$.

We extend the notion of $\vec{A}(D)$ to the realm of signed digraphs. In a signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, where $D = (V, \mathcal{A})$ is a digraph called *underlying digraph of S* and $\sigma : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{+, -\}$ is a function. The *Smarandachely antipodal signed digraph* $\vec{A}(S) = (\vec{A}(D), \sigma')$ of a signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ is a signed digraph whose underlying digraph is $\vec{A}(D)$ called *antipodal digraph* and sign of any arc $e = \vec{uv}$ in $\vec{A}(S)$, $\sigma'(e) = \mu(u)\mu(v)$, where for any $v \in V$, $\mu(v) = \prod_{u \in N(v)} \sigma(uv)$.

Further, a signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ is called *Smarandachely antipodal signed digraph*, if $S \cong \vec{A}(S')$, for some signed digraph S' . The following result indicates the limitations of the notion $\vec{A}(S)$ as introduced above, since the entire class of unbalanced signed digraphs is forbidden to be antipodal signed digraphs.

Proposition 2.1. For any signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, its Smarandachely antipodal signed graph $A(S)$ is balanced.

Proof. Since sign of any arc $e = \overrightarrow{uv}$ in $\overrightarrow{A}(S)$ is $\mu(u)\mu(v)$, where μ is the canonical marking of S , by Proposition 1.1, $\overrightarrow{A}(S)$ is balanced.

For any positive integer k , the k^{th} iterated antipodal signed digraph $\overrightarrow{A}(S)$ of S is defined as follows:

$$\overrightarrow{A}^0(S) = S, A^k(S) = \overrightarrow{A}(\overrightarrow{A}^{k-1}(S)).$$

Corollary 2.2. For any signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ and any positive integer k , $\overrightarrow{A}^k(S)$ is balanced.

In [2], the authors characterized those digraphs that are isomorphic to their antipodal digraphs.

Proposition 2.3.[2] For a digraph $D = (V, \mathcal{A})$, $D \cong \overrightarrow{A}(D)$ if, and only if, $D \cong K_p^*$.

Proof. First, suppose that $D \cong \overrightarrow{A}(D)$. If $(u, v) \in \mathcal{A}$ then $(u, v) \in \mathcal{A}(\overrightarrow{A}(D))$. Therefore, $d_D(u, v) = 1 = \text{diam}(D)$. Since K_p^* is the only digraph of diameter 1, we have $D \cong K_p^*$.

For the converse, if $D \cong K_p^*$, then $\text{diam}(D) = 1$ and for every pair u, v of vertices in D , the distance $d_D(u, v) = 1$. Hence, $\overrightarrow{A}(D) \cong K_p^*$ and $D \cong \overrightarrow{A}(D)$.

We now characterize the signed digraphs that are switching equivalent to their Smarandachely antipodal signed graphs.

Proposition 2.4. For any signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, $S \sim \overrightarrow{A}(S)$ if, and only if, $D \cong K_p^*$ and S is balanced signed digraph.

Proof. Suppose $S \sim \overrightarrow{A}(S)$. This implies, $D \cong \overrightarrow{A}(D)$ and hence D is K_p^* . Now, if S is any signed digraph with underlying digraph as K_p^* , Proposition 2.1 implies that $\overrightarrow{A}(S)$ is balanced and hence if S is unbalanced and its $\overrightarrow{A}(S)$ being balanced can not be switching equivalent to S in accordance with Proposition 1.2. Therefore, S must be balanced.

Conversely, suppose that S is an balanced signed digraph and D is K_p^* . Then, since $\overrightarrow{A}(S)$ is balanced as per Proposition 2.1 and since $D \cong \overrightarrow{A}(D)$, the result follows from Proposition 1.2 again.

Proposition 2.5. For any two signed digraphs S and S' with the same underlying digraph, their Smarandachely antipodal signed digraphs are switching equivalent.

Proposition 2.6.[2] For a digraph $D = (V, \mathcal{A})$, $\overline{D} \cong \overrightarrow{A}(D)$ if, and only if,

- i) $\text{diam}(D) = 2$.
- ii) D is not strongly connected and for every pair u, v of vertices of D , the distance $d_D(u, v) = 1$ or $d_D(u, v) = \infty$.

In view of the above, we have the following result for signed digraphs:

Proposition 2.7. For any signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, $\overline{S} \sim \overrightarrow{A}(S)$ if, and only if, D satisfies conditions of Proposition 2.6.

Proof. Suppose that $\overrightarrow{A}(S) \sim \overline{S}$. Then clearly we have $\overrightarrow{A}(D) \cong \overline{D}$ and hence D satisfies conditions of Proposition 2.6.

Conversely, suppose that D satisfies conditions of Proposition 2.6. Then $\overline{D} \cong \overrightarrow{A}(D)$ by Proposition 2.6. Now, if S is a signed digraph with underlying digraph satisfies conditions of Proposition 2.6, by definition of complementary signed digraph and Proposition 2.1, \overline{S} and $\overrightarrow{A}(S)$ are balanced and hence, the result follows from Proposition 1.2.

The notion of *negation* $\eta(S)$ of a given signed digraph S defined in [6] as follows: $\eta(S)$ has the same underlying digraph as that of S with the sign of each arc opposite to that given to it

in S . However, this definition does not say anything about what to do with nonadjacent pairs of vertices in S while applying the unary operator $\eta(\cdot)$ of taking the negation of S .

Proposition 2.4 & 2.7 provides easy solutions to two other signed digraph switching equivalence relations, which are given in the following results.

Corollary 2.8. For any signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, $S \sim \vec{A}(\eta(S))$.

Corollary 2.9. For any signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, $\bar{S} \sim \vec{A}(\eta(S))$.

Problem. Characterize signed digraphs for which

- i) $\eta(S) \sim \vec{A}(S)$.
- ii) $\eta(\bar{S}) \sim \vec{A}(S)$.

For a signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, the $\vec{A}(S)$ is balanced (Proposition 2.1). We now examine, the conditions under which negation $\eta(S)$ of $\vec{A}(S)$ is balanced.

Proposition 2.10. Let $S = (D, \sigma)$ be a signed digraph. If $\vec{A}(G)$ is bipartite then $\eta(\vec{A}(S))$ is balanced.

Proof. Since, by Proposition 2.1, $\vec{A}(S)$ is balanced, if each semicycle C in $\vec{A}(S)$ contains even number of negative arcs. Also, since $\vec{A}(D)$ is bipartite, all semicycles have even length; thus, the number of positive arcs on any semicycle C in $\vec{A}(S)$ is also even. Hence $\eta(\vec{A}(S))$ is balanced.

§3. Characterization of Smarandachely antipodal signed graphs

The following result characterize signed digraphs which are Smarandachely antipodal signed digraphs.

Proposition 3.1. A signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ is a Smarandachely antipodal signed digraph if, and only if, S is balanced signed digraph and its underlying digraph D is an antipodal graph.

Proof. Suppose that S is balanced and D is a $\vec{A}(D)$. Then there exists a digraph H such that $\vec{A}(H) \cong D$. Since S is balanced, by Proposition 1.1, there exists a marking μ of D such that each arc \vec{uv} in S satisfies $\sigma(\vec{uv}) = \mu(u)\mu(v)$. Now consider the signed digraph $S' = (H, \sigma')$, where for any arc e in H , $\sigma'(e)$ is the marking of the corresponding vertex in D . Then clearly, $\vec{A}(S') \cong S$. Hence S is an Smarandachely antipodal signed digraph.

Conversely, suppose that $S = (D, \sigma)$ is a Smarandachely antipodal signed digraph. Then there exists a signed digraph $S' = (H, \sigma')$ such that $\vec{A}(S') \cong S$. Hence D is the $A(D)$ of H and by Proposition 2.1, S is balanced.

Acknowledgement

The first two authors would like to acknowledge and extend their heartfelt gratitude to Sri. B. Premnath Reddy, Chairman, Acharya Institutes, for his vital encouragement and support.

References

- [1] J. A. Bondy and U. S. R. Murty, Graph Theory with Applications, MacMillan, London, 1976.
- [2] G. Johns and K. Sleno, Antipodal graphs and digraphs, *Internat. J. Math. & Math. Sci.*, **16**(1993), No. 3, 579-586.
- [3] F. Harary, R. Norman and D. Cartwright, Structural models: An introduction to the theory of directed graphs, J. Wiley, New York, 1965.
- [4] R. Rangarajan and P. Siva Kota Reddy, The edge C_4 signed graph of a signed graph, *Southeast Asian Bull. Math.*, **34**(2010), No. 6, 1077-1082.
- [5] E. Sampathkumar, M. S. Subramanya and P. Siva Kota Reddy, Characterization of Line Sidigraphs, *Southeast Asian Bull. Math.*, to appear.
- [6] P. Siva Kota Reddy, S. Vijay and H. C. Savithri, A Note on Path Sidigraphs, *International J. Math. Combin.*, **1**(2010), 42-46.